

Hill Torrents' Management Options in Koh- e-Suleman Range Pakistan- Community Perspective

*Ghulam Zakir-Hassan^{1,2,3}, Muhammad Shahzad Abdul Rahim¹, Adnan Hassan¹, Jamshaid Farid⁴, Matloob Ahmad⁵

¹Irrigation Research Institute (IRI), Government of the Punjab, Irrigation Department, Library Road, Lahore 54500, Pakistan.

²School of Agricultural, Environmental and Veterinary Sciences (SAEVS), Charles Sturt University (CSU), Albury, NSW 2640, Australia

³Gulbali Institute, Charles Sturt University, Albury, NSW 2640, Australia

⁴The Help Foundation, Kot Mithan, Rajanpur,, Punjab, Pakistan

⁵Ghazi University, DG Khan, Pakistan

Submission Date: 05 March 2023 | Published Date: 20 May 2023

*Corresponding author: Ghulam Zakir-Hassan

Irrigation Research Institute (IRI), Government of the Punjab, Irrigation Department, Library Road, Lahore 54500, Pakistan.

Abstract

Hill Torrent is a flash hill stream with steep slopes, prone to sudden surges of high volumes of water after rain in the catchment area carrying high sediment loads which causes heavy loss to the infrastructure, population, livestock and livelihood etc. If harnessed and managed properly, this water can play a vital role in national growth by contributing as a significant water resource. Punjab Irrigation Department (PID) intends to adopt some suitable options for the management of hill torrents in the Koh-e-Suleman Range (KSR) to control the damages and regulate the water for better use. Opinions of community living in the study area since ancient times can be of vital importance for the harvesting and sustainable utilization of this water resource. A consultative seminar was organized in the region to obtain the viewpoint of stakeholders at grass root level in a broader community perspective. The event was organized by Irrigation Research Institute (IRI) of PID in collaboration with Ghazi University and the Help Foundation at Ghazi University, Dera Ghazi Khan. The event was attended by a wide spectrum of stakeholders ranging from the Federal Government experts to the local inhabitants. It was recommended that Integrated Hill Torrent Management (IHTM) should be the best option. For IHTM model, all concerned departments should work in close coordination with each other and with the local farmers/stakeholders by putting in the integrated efforts. Construction of dams, dispersion structures and ponds are the proposed management options for the storage of water in the catchment areas. Management options for storage of water, its application/use and dispersion of water in pachad area can vary from site to site but these should not disturb the centuries-old indigenous system of rights and entitlement being practiced in the regio

Keywords: Hill Torrents, Koh-e-Suleman, Dera Ghazi Khan, Community, Punjab, Pakistan

INTRODUCTION

The term torrent is utilized for water carrier channels carrying flash water flows; the term is mostly utilized for steep mountainous rivers generating rapid runoff. Locally these types of channels are termed as "Rodh Kohi" (Zakir-Hassan et al., 2022). The torrential area of Dera Ghazi (D.G.) Khan and Rajanpur Districts of Punjab province is situated between the Indus River and the KSMR surrounded by the province of Sindh, Baluchistan in the west and Khyber Pakhtunkhwa (KPK) in the North. About forty-five percent of the total catchment areas lie in the two districts and the remaining 55% in the province of Baluchistan. The area in the west (on the right side of the Indus River) which is unirrigated by local canal irrigation network is piedmont area locally known as "Pachad" area and is fertile due to

unexploited sediment deposits of the mountains brought down with flood water. Pachad area is considered to be an area between darrah (the point after which torrent enters the plains) and the right bank of Indus River. The torrential area of the two districts consists of thirteen (13) major Hill torrents extending from Kaura and ending at Sori Janubi (Saleem et al., 2023). Hill torrents management and use of this big water resource for irrigation is a neglected subject in Pakistan (Ahmad & Choudhry, 2005).

Hill torrents carry high sediment loads during flash floods emanating from the mountain ranges. There are 200 hill torrents- minor, medium & major, of which 13 are major, originate from Koh-e-Suleman Range (KSR) and flow through D.G Khan and Rajanpur districts towards the River Indus. The catchment area of these hill torrents is 30772 Km². The area extends over a length of 360 Km from Ramak to Kashmore, while in width it varies from 25 Km to 40 Km. The area between the foothills of the KSR from Ramak to Kashmore and Chashma Right bank Canal System and D.G Khan Canal System is locally known as Piedmont area. The location of major hill torrents originating from KSR in D G Khan and Rajan Pur districts is shown in Fig 1.

Fig 1: Map showing locations of major hill torrents originating from KSR in Pakistan

The hill torrents bring flashy floods of shorter duration and higher magnitude. Flood water from the hill torrents is used for irrigation with the piedmont area, through a network of diversion and dispersion structures. Geographically Suleman range lies between longitude 69° 10' E to 70° 49' E and serves as a divide line between KPK, Baluchistan and Punjab province. Climate of the area is arid. Rainfall varies between 125 mm to 375 mm and its distribution is uneven, erratic and patchy. Concentration of rain fall / precipitation is mostly in the month of July and August (monsoon period). Steep slope from Darrah to D.G Khan Canal is 10-15 ft/mile. Velocity of hill torrent flood water varies from 6-8 ft/sec, and flow rates vary considerably; which is classified as shown in **Table 1**.

Table-1: Classification of hill

Sr. No.	Type/Class	Flow (ft ³ /sec)
1	Minor	5000
2	Medium	5000-1500
3	Major	> 15000

In DG Khan irrigation zone, 13 hill torrents are classified as major hill torrents having discharge over 15000 cusecs out of which seven major hill torrents are in DG Khan District and six in Rajanpur district. Out of these thirteen, 4 hill

torrents (Vidore, Mithawan, Kaha and Chachar) have been chosen where plan for the construction of dam for capturing flood water is under process. The flood water brings high silt content in the plain areas and thus precluded flood management by dams or detention reservoirs. The silting and scouring phenomena are largely responsible for frequent changes in flow regime and shifting of flow paths of hill torrents (Zakir-Hassan et al., 2022). A view of two hill torrents is shown in Fig 2.

Fig 2: A view of Vidore and Kaha Hill Torrents in Koh-e-Suleman Range in Pakistan

In nature nothing is static; dynamic is the law of nature. The rigid and stable mountains and valleys which appear to us to be ever in existence are under the same law of nature and are being slowly eroded and removed from one place to be deposited at another. The rigid rocks and the surface soils are being constantly disintegrated, fragmented and carried out from place to place; which is the principal factor causing the production of sediment in water. It appears in the form of precipitation. At certain elevations, it rains whereas at other it snows. Sediment is a naturally occurring material that is broken down by processes of weathering and erosion, and is subsequently transported by the action of wind, water, or ice, and/or by the force of gravity acting on the particles. For example, sand and silt can be carried in suspension in river water and on reaching the sea be deposited by sedimentation and if buried this may eventually become sandstone and siltstone called the sedimentary rocks (Qureshi et al., 2016).

Water is the major medium which transports soil materials. It helps to sort out various sizes of particles. It carries these from steeper slopes into depressions. Deposits of sand silt and even thick soils are the result of water transportation and deposition. Winds is another sediment transporting materials. It is more effective to transport granular materials. Dry sands and silts are carried over long distances often several hundreds of miles from their place of origin by storms. Large quantities of materials are blown with winds. Flash floods originating from the hill-torrents cause huge damage to infrastructure and loss of human and animal lives. For example, flood 2022, caused damages to 150 bridges and 3500 km roads, 2 million-acre of crops and orchards, and 107 000 animals have been destroyed (Saleem et al., 2023). Management of these hill torrents is imperative to avoid/minimize flood damages as well to enhance irrigated agriculture. Different engineering (constructions) solutions have been studies and proposed for example (Ahmad et al., 2016; Qureshi et al., 2016; Saleem et al., 2023). Hill torrents in Pakistan annually generate a water resource of about 23

billion cubic meter (BCM), which is not harvested and used effectively for sustainable water management in the country (Ahmad et al., 2016). A study carried out by (Zakir-Hassan et al., 2022) found that the excessive sediment loads transported by these hill torrents is a major hurdle in the storage of this water.

The objective of the current study is to investigate and dig-down the stakeholder's perspective, what solutions the local people suggest, what are their thoughts. For this purpose, the event was arranged in the study area at grassroots level to ensure maximum participation of local community.

METHODOLOGY

This study focused on the hill torrents emanating from the KSR in two districts (Dera Ghazi Khan and Rajanpur) of the Punjab province of Pakistan. A one-day National Seminar was arranged by IRI in the study area in collaboration of Ghazi University, Dera Ghazi Khan and the Help Foundation (an NGO) district Rajan Pur (Ghulam Zakir Hassan, 2018; IRI, 2018). Main focus of the seminar was to bring all the stakeholders at one platform and get the point of view of the inhabitants about the management interventions for hill torrents. Therefore, the event was organized at local level within the study area and all the other participants from the public and private sectors were invited from across the country. More than 80 delegates/stakeholders representing different provincial and federal government departments, universities, private sector organization/individuals, consultants, NGOs and representatives of local farmers participated in the event as tabulated in Appendix A. The Minister for Punjab Irrigation Department (PID) chaired the seminar (Fig 4). The seminar was arranged in four sessions in the following sequence:-

- i. Inaugural Session;
- ii. Technical Session
- iii. Panel Discussion
- iv. Concluding Session

Fig 3: Participants of the seminar on hill torrents management held at Ghazi University DG Khan Pakistan

Inaugural Session

Mr. Ghulam Zakir Hassan Sial, Director IRI welcomed the participants and paid tributes to all delegates to participate in the event and especially the chief Guest Minister Irrigation, Mr. Muhammad Mohsin Leghari. He briefed the participants that Irrigation Research Institute (IRI) established in 1924, is a leading institute in the country for research and model studies pertaining to water sector issues. He apprised about the themes/objectives of the seminar and requested all the participants to highlight the issues related to the topic and give suggestions to achieve the objectives of the event in a fruitful manner. He expressed his views that “Hill Torrents Management is a big concern now a days and we are all here today to discuss this issue and to get the community perspective”.

Mr. Fazal Karim, Superintendent Engineer, Project Circle D.G Khan Irrigation Zone presented the Keynote presentation. He elaborated that “There are almost 200 Hill torrents (Major, Medium and Minor) in KSR, out of which 13 are Major (7 in D.G Khan District while 6 in Rajanpur District) Hill Torrents. He further described the history, peak discharges and statistics of the major Hill Torrents. He briefed about the previous and ongoing studies/ plans of these Hill Torrents. He apprised the participants about the steps/initiatives taken by Punjab Irrigation Department, including remodeling and rehabilitation of flood carrying channels. In the end, he highlighted the impacts of these projects on livelihood of people, flood control and economy of the area.

Sardar Muhammad Mohsin Leghari, Minister Punjab Irrigation Department addressed the participants that in the past, the water from Hill Torrents was not properly managed and utilized and he himself was the victim of this flash flooding. This Govt. is willing to work on a sustainable solution for these problems and Irrigation Research Institute (IRI) is playing a vital role here by organizing this event. He expressed his hope that this gathering of stakeholders will end up in providing better recommendations to the Government. The Minister showed his keen interest in the seminar and requested all the participants especially the farming community for their active participation and input.

Technical Session

Technical session was chaired by Sardar Muhammad Mohsin Leghari Minister Irrigation Department and co-chaired by Mr. Khawar Nazir Chief Engineer D. G Khan and Mr. Qasim Saeed Chief Engineer Drainage and Flood Zone of Punjab Irrigation Department. The technical presentations given in Table 2 were delivered by the distinguished speakers from all over the country. Pictorial view of some of the speakers are shown in Fig 4.

Table-2: Names of Speakers and their titles

Sr. No.	Name of Speaker	Title of the Presentation
1	Ghulam Zakir Hassan Sial (Director, Irrigation Research Institute Lahore)	Sediment Challenges in Hill Torrents Management
2	Kareem Nawaz (Expert/Country Coordinator Spate Irrigation Network Pakistan/Meta Meta Holland)	Spate Irrigation History and Potential in Pakistan
3	Dr. Matloob Ahmed (Lecturer, Ghazi University D.G. Khan)	Irrigation Practices and Issues in Hill Torrents Command Area of D.G. Khan
4	Dr. Arshad Ashraf Principal Scientific Officer, Climate, Energy and Water Research Institute, NARC, Ministry of National Food Security and Research, Govt. of Pakistan, Islamabad	Resource Potential of Hill Torrents Region of Pakistan- opportunities and constraints
5	Mr. Najeeb Ullah Khosa Superintending Engineer WAPDA, DG Khan	Hill Torrents Management- Interventions by WAPDA
6	Dr. Muhammad Mushtaq (Divisional Forest Officer, Range Management Division, Dera Ghazi Khan)	Water and Soil Conservation Through Water Spreading Bunds in Rangelands of Dera Ghazi Khan

Figure-4:
Glimpses of
Distinguished
Speakers-
Expressing
their views in
the technical
session of the
Seminar

Mr. Ghulam Zakir Hassan Sial, (Director IRI) highlighted that sediment challenges are a big hurdle in the management of Hill Torrents which flow along the flash water after rain fall in the catchment area of the Hill Torrents. In this context IRI and ISRIP had already conducted a Sediment Study on four Hill Torrents (Vidore, Mithawan, Kaha and Chachar) in DG Khan during flood season 2016. Chemical analysis of sediment samples collected from the sites were carried out and sediment load was calculated. He also shared the results among delegates/participants concluded from that study by telling that on the average 10.2, 24, 5.8 and 27.4 acre feet per square mile per annum sediment load were found from Vidore, Mithawan, Kaha and Chachar hill torrents respectively. He emphasized their one year sediment study is not enough to design the storage reservoir and IRI is planning to carry it out for another 3 to 4 years.

Kareem Nawaz (Expert/Country Coordinator Spate Irrigation Network Pakistan/Meta Meta Holland) focused on spate Irrigation. He expressed that Rod Kohi system is an old system which came from the Arab region. . When floods come, it creates benefits and sometimes create disaster. Spate irrigation is an ancient practice by which flash floodwater is diverted by gravity onto farmland situated at a lower elevation than the flood water. Spate Irrigation deserves more

attention, which can save us from disasters. He showed that 17.133 million acres can be irrigated from this water and there is a potential of 18.68 million acre feet (MAF) water, that can be harvested.

Dr. Matloob Ahmed (Lecturer, Ghazi University D.G. Khan) focused on the constraints of Hill Torrents. He also described about the salient features of command area of Mithawan Hill Torrents and methods of irrigation in that area. He described that Sedimentation (63 g/L) creates a hard layer on the upper surface of soil that reduce its workability for agriculture. At the end he also described about the possible solutions of Hill Torrents water resource Management, which include different types of hydraulic structures as well.

Dr. Arshad Ashraf (Principal Scientific Officer, Climate, Energy and Water Research Institute, NARC, Ministry of National Food Security and Research, Govt. of Pakistan, Islamabad) emphasized on issues of Rod Kohi Spate Irrigation Systems of all over the country for which structures can be used for water distribution systems in three formats i.e technical, climatic and social issues. Single gated structures and multi-gated structures can be used for Water diversion. At the end he concluded that water conservation potential should be utilized through construction of small/mini dams, farm ponds and adopting high efficiency irrigation techniques like rain-gun, drip-irrigation systems to enhance water as well as agriculture productivity. He presented a case study of D.G Khan and Rajanpur Hill Torrents region. He showed that bank erosion of cultivated fields was avoided by construction of a retaining wall at 120m length. He described different hydraulic structures for improvement in application efficiency.

Najeeb Ullah Khosa (Superintending Engineer WAPDA, DG Khan) emphasized on the objectives and progress of Murunj Dam Project on Kaha Hill Torrent. He also described about the salient features of the Murunj Dam Project including a gauging station installed on Kaha Nullah at Harand, about 25 km downstream of proposed dam site from which daily flow and sediment data had been recorded/measured since 2013. At the end he shared the field activities and current status of the Project. He expressed that non-allocation/release of funds is the main obstacle in Murunj Dam Project and still waited from Ministry of Planning Development and Reforms (MOPD&R) Islamabad.

Dr. Muhammad Mushtaq (Divisional Forest Officer, Range Management Division, Dera Ghazi Khan) focused on bed stabilization techniques by forestation and other measures. He also requested Minister Irrigation that few Instruments might be provided to poor farmers for bringing up prosperity among local people. In Tribal area, there is no water for survival, so small check dams are the dire need of this area. Drinking water reservoirs should be constructed. He presented the activities being taken up by Forest Department in the Hill Torrents areas. He presented how plantation of trees reduced soil erosion in the area.

Panel Discussion

All the participants were invited to express their view and ask questions from the experts regarding their opinion. Mr. Jamshaid Farid, while moderating the panel discussion session place four following questions before the panel and request to respond on these questions one by one on their turn.

- ❖ What are the major challenges for Hill Torrents Management?
- ❖ What are the potential areas/ benefits of Hill Torrents Harnessing?
- ❖ What are the impacts of global climatic changes on Hill Torrents?
- ❖ What are options/sustainable solutions for Hill Torrents Management?

The members of the panel with their roles are tabulated in Table 3, while glimpses of some participants expressing their views are shown in Figure 5.

Table-3: Name of members for panel discussion and their role

Sr. No.	Name and Designation/ Department	Role
1.	Mr. Jamshaid Farid, Executive Coordinator, Help Foundation	Moderator
2.	Mr. Muhammad Shahzad Abdul Rahim, Assistant Director, IRI, Lahore	Minute Taker
3.	Muhammad Qasim Saeed Chief Engineer, Punjab Irrigation Department.	Panelist/E xpert
4.	Prof. Dr. Muhammad Iqbal Dean, Faculty of Agricultural Sciences, Ghazi University DG Khan	Panelist/E xpert
5.	Mr. Allah Bakhsh Project Coordinator, Spate Irrigation, Strengthening Participatory Organization (SPO)	Panelist/E xpert
6.	Mr. Anwar ul Haq Shehzad Director, On Farm Water Management, Agriculture Department. DG Khan	Panelist/E xpert
7.	Muhammad Qasim Qureshi Progressive Farmer	Panelist/E xpert

The Experts in the panel discussed about the issues regarding the Challenges in Hill Torrents Management and gave their suggestions in the light of their experience.

Mr. Qasim Saeed expressed the views about Management of Hill Torrents e.g., storage of small check dam, watershed management, growing of vegetation may reduce the sediment. Also grazing of animals may be controlled and dispersion / rigid structures are sustainable solution for hill torrents management. He showed a concern about the challenges of Sediment for dams in Hill Torrents areas.

Dr. Muhammad Iqbal expressed his views that there is not a single solution but integrated approach for hill torrents management is required. By growing trees, flow velocity can be reduced, involvement of stakeholders is primarily important, construction of dispersive structures will reduce the intensity of flow, Legislation for groundwater pumping is necessary and also poor quality water pumping may be controlled. By water-shed management, problem of erosion can be controlled. Small control structures can be constructed.

Mr. Allah Bakhsh Suggested to construct inlet/ outlet water management structure. There is a need of three types of water management (Irregular levels, canal levels and at tiled level). Gated structures near canal may be made for avoiding erosion. Earth moving machines are also needed for development of the area.

Mr. Anwar ul Haq recommended that harnessing of water in catchment area through retaining walls, small check dams, storage structures and water shed management are the solutions of these challenges. He also apprised the participants about the role of On Farm Water Management (OFWM) in management of these flash flooding. He highlighted the various facilities/interventions being provided by the Punjab Agriculture Department like sprinkler/drip irrigation system, laser land levelling, soil and water testing lab facilities, geophysical investigations for installation of tube wells, earth moving machinery, lining of water courses etc. He added that the Agriculture Department will extend all on farm services in the areas of Hill Torrents.

Community Perspective

During Panel Discussion session, a kind of interactive session was also started and the participants were invited for open house discussions and questions/answers.

Mr. Qasim Qureshi, being a progressive farmer - representing the farming community – suggested that sediments are blessings. Retaining walls can minimize the high velocity of the flash water. Spate practices are required to retain the water in command area. Small projects are needed instead of large projects to cope with the challenges in management of Hill Torrents, as in large projects a lot of time and money is wasted for their feasibility and design aspects.

Other farmers/inhabitants also showed their keen interest in the open discussions and the experts responded to them by possible solutions of their issues. Some of the demands raised by the farmers are as follows:

- i. Farmers belonging to catchment areas complained that there is no system to store the water coming from hills during flood season and it passes very quickly.
- ii. Demanded for construction of small check dam in tribal area.
- iii. Drinking water reservoirs may be arranged depending upon the population in catchment areas.
- iv. Demand for supply of bulldozer/machinery and also solar system for land levelling and irrigation practices.
- v. Farmers raised their voice that they are not made part of planning and decision making process.

Conclusions and Recommendations

After Panel Discussion, the following recommendations/solutions were drawn up to cope with the challenges in the management of Hill Torrents as per community perspective.

Sr. No.	Recommendations/Proposed Actions	Actions proposed to be taken by:
A) Management Options in Catchment area		
1.	Construction of Hydraulic Structures for Hill Torrents Management/Watershed management including small dams, water spreading dams, delay action dams, check dams, single and multi-gated water dispersive structures, Inlet and outlet structures in catchment areas, farm ponds, diversion spurs, bunds, sedimentation basins, flood-spreading weirs, construction	Punjab Irrigation Department Soil Conservation Directorate & other Departments

Sr. No.	Recommendations/Proposed Actions	Actions proposed to be taken by:
	of leaky dams at catchment area to reduce the velocity of water and sediment load, bed fixer in the deeply eroded water channels, terracing at highly eroded catchment area, gate operated water diversion structures in the Wah and bund to bund connection through permanent field outlets and other site specific structures.	
2.	Construction of Loose Stone Wall, Gully plugging, Earthen Band, Ponds (up to 30 acre ft storage)	Soil Conservation, Agriculture Department DG Khan
3.	Proper assessment of sediment loads in hill torrents and sediment transport mechanism for 3-4 years	Punjab Irrigation Department /IRI
4.	Afforestation (xerophytes) of already existing plants like Acacia Arabica (kikar), Acacia modesta (phulahi), Dodonia viscosa (sanatha), Prosopis spicigera (Jand), Tamarix articulate (Farash), Zizyphous jujube (ber)	Forest Department DG Khan
5.	Catchment Area Development including Intensive forestation & vegetation management.	Forest Department, Agriculture Department LG&CD Department
6.	Drinking water ponds in catchment areas	Housing Urban Development- Public Health Engineering (HUD&PHED) Department
B) Hill Torrents Channel Management		
7.	Construction of Gabion spur, Retaining wall, Bed bar, Diversion band	Soil Conservation, Agriculture Department
C) Management Options in Pachad area		
8.	Involvement of local communities in the relevant interventions	All Departments
9.	Proper utilization of available water for irrigation purpose to bring land under Rodh-Kohi cultivation/irrigation.	Punjab Irrigation Department, Agriculture Department
10.	Construction of storage/farm ponds for fisheries/ ground water recharge /other uses.	Fisheries Department Agriculture Department
11.	Spate Irrigation System and its development	Agriculture Department
12.	Water scarcity to be managed through rainwater harvesting; groundwater recharging, water recycling and re-use;	Punjab Irrigation Department, Agriculture Department All other Departments

Sr. No.	Recommendations/Proposed Actions	Actions proposed to be taken by:
	sedimentation & pollution control measures etc.	
13.	Livelihood of local rural communities should be given preference/should be taken on board/consulted.	All Departments
14.	Provision of solar system and machinery for farmers including bulldozers etc. for efficient use of available water.	Agriculture Department
15.	Groundwater resources assessment and management	Irrigation Research Institute (IRI)/Punjab Irrigation Department
16.	Flow Monitoring, Forecasting and warning by use of latest real time tools/instruments etc.	Punjab Irrigation Department, WAPDA, Pakistan Meteorological Department (PMD), National Disaster Management Authority (NDMA)
17.	Soil conservation practices to control soil erosions, gully grating, check dams, vegetated waterway, strip cropping etc.	Soil Conservation, Punjab Agriculture Department
18.	Master Plan for Hill Torrent Managements	Punjab Irrigation Department
19.	Watershed Management Interventions	Punjab Irrigation Department, Punjab Agriculture Department

It was concluded that Integrated Hill Torrent Management should be adapted, for which all Departments should work in close coordination with each other and the local farmers/stakeholders and integrated efforts should be made for the issues. Construction of dams, dispersion structures and ponds are the management options for storage of water in the catchment areas, while separate management options for storage of water, its application/use and dispersion of water in pachad area are needed. It will result in proper management of hill torrents, flood controls, improved agriculture/livestock activities for better livelihood.

Acknowledgments

The contributions by the Chief Guest, speakers, media persons, university administration, Help Foundation, all experts, farming community, and IRI staff in making this event successful are acknowledged. Funding for the event was provide by Irrigation Department, Government of the Punjab, which I also acknowledged.

Annexure A: List of Participating Organizations/ Departments in the Seminar

Sr. No.	Name of Department/Organization
A- Federal/Provincial Departments	
1.	Water and Power Development Authority (WAPDA)
2.	Ministry of Food Security and Research, NARC, Islamabad
3.	Punjab Agriculture Department
4.	Punjab Forest Department
5.	Punjab Livestock and Dairy Development Department (LS & DD)
6.	Punjab Mines and Minerals Department
7.	On Farm Water Management (OFWM) D G. Khan
8.	Pakistan Bureau of Statistics, Multan
B- Irrigation Department	

Sr. No.	Name of Department/Organization
1.	Minister, Punjab Irrigation Department
2.	Irrigation Research Institute (IRI) Lahore
3.	Irrigation, Dera Ghazi Khan Zone
4.	Irrigation, Multan Zone
5.	Irrigation Drainage and Flood (D&F) Zone
6.	Punjab Irrigation and Drainage Authority (PIDA)
C- Universities	
1.	Ghazi University, Dera Ghazi Khan.
2.	Baha ud Din Zakaria University, Multan
D- NGO's and Individual/ Stakeholder	
1.	Help Foundation
2.	Doaba Foundation
3.	Farmers from Dera Ghazi Khan District
4.	Farmers from Rajanpur District
5.	Farmers from Dera Ismail Khan District
E- Media Groups	
1.	Pakistan Television (PTV)
2.	Such TV
3.	Duniya News
4.	Jang News
5.	Nawa-e- Waqt News
6.	Khabrain News
7.	92- News
8.	Osaf News
9.	Jahan Pakistan News
10.	Pakistan News
11.	Express News

Notes:

- i. Authors declare no conflict of interest
- ii. The views expressed in the paper are the authors' own and do not reflect the point of view of any department or organization.
- iii. Cooperation extended by field formation of DG Khan Irrigation Zone in data collection and field survey; and provision of funds by the Punjab Irrigation Department (PID) are acknowledged

REFERENCES

1. Ahmad, M., Arshad, M., Masud Cheema, M. J., & Ahmad, R. (2016). Comparison of Available Water Resources for Irrigation in Mithawan Hill Torrent Command Area of Dera Ghazi Khan, Pakistan. *Pakistan Journal of Agricultural Sciences*, 53(01), 233-240. doi:10.21162/pakjas/16.4570
2. Ahmad, M., & Choudhry, M. R. (2005). Farmers' Irrigation Practices Under Rod Kohi Irrigation System. *Pakistan Journal of Water Resources*, 9(1).
3. Ghulam Zakir Hassan, A. H., Muhammad Shahzad Abdul Rahim, Summaya Nosheen. (2018). Summary of the National Seminar on Hill Torrents Management - Sediment Challenges and options at Ghazi University, Dera Ghazi Khan. (IRR-PHY-SD/02), 1-20.

4. IRI. (2018). Hill Torrents Management- Sediment Challenges and Options: Summary of One Day National Seminar at Ghazi University, Report No IRR-PHY-SD/02, Irrigation Reserach Institute (IRI), Lahore, Pakistan.
5. Qureshi, M. M., Rashid, M. U., Shah, M. A., & Baluch, M. A. (2016). Hill Torrent Management in Southern Punjab of Pakistan: Historic Perspective and New Trends. echnical Journal, University of Engineering and Technology (UET) Taxila, 21(II).
6. Saleem, M., Arfan, M., Ansari, K., & Hassan, D. (2023). Analyzing the Impact of Ungauged Hill Torrents on the Riverine Floods of the River Indus: A Case Study of Koh E Suleiman Mountains in the DG Khan and Rajanpur Districts of Pakistan. Resources, 12(2). doi:10.3390/resources12020026
7. Zakir-Hassan, G., Shabir, G., Hassan, A., Rahim, M. S. A., & Noshin, S. (2022). Sediments for hill torrents management- Challenges and options in D G Khan Area in Pakistan. Global J Res Agri Life Sci., 26, 28-37. doi:<https://gjrpublication.com/wp-content/uploads/2023/01/GJRALS260150.pdf>